

An immersive approach to visualising the local impact of sea level rise on flood risks

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Abstract. Climate change is a global phenomenon that is frequently described at a global scale using numeric values (e.g. "1.5 degree increase in temperature globally"), diagrams, or maps depicting future scenarios. However, specific local impacts can differ drastically from global changes and understanding them based on those descriptions can be difficult. Therefore, the work presented here proposes an interactive system that visualizes the local consequences of the sea level rise in combination with various flooding scenarios (annual, five, ten, and 100 year flood) for different climate change predictions. The system enables users to explore flood impacts dynamically from the point of view of a pedestrian, offering an alternative to map-based representations. Results from a preliminary user study indicate that the system performs similar to map representations in conveying flood-related information, highlighting its potential as an intuitive and engaging tool for flood risk communication.

Submission Type. Project

BoK Concepts. [CV4] Graphic representation techniques, [GS3] Use of geospatial information

Keywords. visualization, unity, immersive, climate change, flooding

1 Introduction

As climate change is advancing rapidly, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is predicting that there will be an increased frequency and intensity of flood events, as well as a general rise of the sea level (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change, 2023a). This sea level rise could reach approximately 35 cm up to one meter in the next 75 years (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change, 2023b). As (Burningham et al., 2008) has shown, people tend to underestimate the risk of rare and extreme

flooding events and engaging with local perspectives can raise awareness.

In order to address this gap, we present an immersive 3D environment depicting three places in the German city of Hamburg and how they are affected by flooding with respect to different climate prediction scenarios. Our objective is to enable users to understand the local implications of climate change predictions. We conducted a preliminary study with ten participants. The results indicates a change of perception in flood risk awareness.

2 Background

Over the last decade, interactive climate visualization tools enhanced the communication of climate data by allowing users to engage with climate change predictions. These tools include dynamic (web-)maps and localized projections for addressing a diverse audience (Lumley et al., 2022). To further improve the engagement with climate data, projects like ClimSim (Liestøl et al., 2015) or AiR (Mathews et al., 2021) used Augmented Reality to show future climate scenarios. These immersive visualizations can make it easier for a broader audience to interact with and understand future climate scenarios.

Figure 1. Person using the immersive visualization environment to view flood predictions

Figure 2. Screenshot of the system displaying the area in front of the town hall with a projection for the year 2100 during a 5-year flood with the SSP of "unchecked pollution"

We want to expand on this approach by combining immersive visualizations with localised data.

3 System Description

The system depicts a 3D city model created in Unity¹, and allows users to visit three locations in Hamburg, Germany: the Elbphilharmonie, Speicherstadt (port area), and the Town hall square (city center). These can be explored in an immersive visualization environment (IVE)² (see Figure 1) by moving through the virtual environment. The IVE consists of three back-projection screens, which are arranged in a semi-circular manner with a viewing angle of about 114°, each with a size of 200 cm × 150 cm (Ostkamp and Kray, 2014) (see Figure 1). Users can control the visualization by manipulating the following parameters: type of flood (sea level rise plus annual, 5 year, 10 year or 100 year floods), projection (which implement the different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) provided by the IPCC), and the year to project (2020 until 2120). This allows users to autonomously switch between scenarios and explore the effects of climate change on flood events in Hamburg. A screenshot of the interface is provided in Figure 2.

The developed application uses a publicly available open building dataset from the city of Hamburg³ to create a realistic virtual environment to display future flood events. This data was integrated using the ArcGIS SDK for Unity⁴.

4 Evaluation and Discussion

We carried out an initial evaluation of the system with ten participants (all students between 21 and 25 years old). They were shown three kinds of visualizations of climate

change effects: (1) an excerpt from the written IPCC report, (2) an interactive web map created by Climate Central⁵ shown on a laptop, and (3) the immersive visualization presented in this paper (see Figure 1). Participants had to answer a set of Likert-scale questions after having seen each visualization with the results being plotted in Figure 3. All participants started with the IPCC report (C1). We then varied the order of exposure: four participants saw the web map (C2) next and the immersive visualization last (C3), while six participants first the immersive visualization (C4) and then the web map (C5).

Contrary to the port area, participants' expectations for the city center showed a larger shift to their initial assessment of flood risks. Although people often tend to ignore their "at risk" status in relation to flood events (Burningham et al., 2008), after experiencing our proposed system, people rated the future risk of flood events higher for some areas. Hence, we interpret the initial evaluation as hinting at people changing their perception of flood risks when using the proposed system, even though these changes may vary for different circumstances.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents an application for visualizing future local flooding events based on climate change predictions. Our initial evaluation implies that the immersive visualization can change user perception regarding perceived flood risks due to climate change. This change of expectations is similar to what results from a more traditional interactive map approach. Qualitative feedback indicate that the immersive approach can pique a user's interest more than a webmap that requires a potential user to already be interested in the topic.

The system currently only supports one city with three locations. An interesting avenue for expanding the system would be a system that incorporates more locations around the world. In such a case, it would also be interesting to evaluate the user's responses between places that are familiar to them and places that are not.

¹<https://unity.com/>, accessed 29 January 2025

²<https://sitcomlab.github.io/IVE/>, accessed 29 January 2025

³3D-Gebäudemodell LoD3.0-HH Hamburg from Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Landesbetrieb Geoinformation und Vermessung, published under <http://www.govdata.de/dl-de/by-2-0dl-de/by-2-0> at , accessed 29 January 2025

⁴<https://developers.arcgis.com/unity/>, accessed 29 January 2025

⁵<https://coastal.climatecentral.org/map/>

6 Data and Software Availability

The application, study files and study results are available at OSF (<https://osf.io/59bxz/>). The Unity project and source code is not available due to the licenses of assets used.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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Figure 3. Participants responses after each condition: (C1) After seeing IPCC report; (C2) After seeing IPCC report and webmap; (C3) After seeing IPCC report, webmap, and immersive visualization; (C4) After seeing IPCC report and immersive visualization; (C5) After seeing IPCC report, immersive visualization, and webmap.